

Exploring with Technology

The deep-sea is a challenging place and scientists can only visit and collect information from a tiny fraction of the ocean. This makes it impossible to find all of the ecosystems that might need protecting. To help solve this problem ATLAS scientists use technology!

ROV control room - photo credit Covadonga Orejas, MEDWAVES

ROVs (Remotely Operated Vehicles) are underwater robots that are usually controlled by the crew on board a research ship. Scientists sit in the control room with the ROV pilots to help decide what to look at or collect. Many of the deep areas studied in ATLAS have strong ocean currents, so the ROVs for ATLAS need to be big and heavy to do their job.

Gliders are small robots that 'fly' underwater using their wings. They can be controlled via a satellite link from anywhere in the world. They normally have lots of different equipment to collect information such as water temperatures and saltness. They can be at sea for up to seven months at a time!

SAMS gliders. Photo credit: Andy Mogg, SAMS

Computer models can be used to find out how different creatures (e.g. coral larvae) might spread out in the oceans via ocean currents. They can also help scientists to work out where certain creatures might be found based on the information that they have collected so far, without having to actually visit that part of the ocean.

Credit: Alan Fox, University of Edinburgh, ATLAS Project

